

Fixed-Bed Column Adsorption of Methyl Orange Using Watermelon Rind Low-Cost Natural Adsorbents

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ABSTRACT

Synthetic dyes are extensively utilized in textile, leather, and food industries, posing severe environmental challenges when released into water bodies. Among various treatment methods, adsorption offers a cost-effective, efficient, and operationally simple solution for dye removal. This study investigates the adsorption of Methyl Orange (MO) dye from aqueous solutions using abundant and low-cost natural adsorbents: watermelon rind (WMR), in a continuous fixed-bed column setup. Operational parameters such as bed height (1.5 cm to 4.5 cm), influent concentration (50 mg/L to 150 mg/L), and flow rate (5 mL/min to 15 mL/min) were systematically varied to assess performance. The resulting breakthrough curves were analysed using the Thomas and Yoon–Nelson kinetic models to determine bed capacity and kinetic parameters. The experimental findings revealed excellent performance from watermelon rind, achieving 90.9–95.1% dye removal. The kinetic models provided a strong fit for the experimental data, with R² values consistently exceeding 0.95. Watermelon rind is shown to be a highly promising, eco-friendly, and sustainable alternative for industrial wastewater treatment applications.

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1. Introduction

Water pollution due to synthetic dyes is one of the major environmental problems today. Dyes are widely used in textile, paper, plastic, leather, and printing industries. Among these, Methyl Orange, an anionic azo dye, is known for its toxicity and persistence in aquatic environments. Its discharge without proper treatment can lead to serious ecological impacts. Conventional treatment methods such as coagulation, oxidation, and membrane filtration are expensive and less effective for dilute dye solutions. In recent years, biosorption using natural and low-cost materials like fruit peels and agricultural residues has gained significant attention. Watermelon rind, which is often discarded as waste, contains functional groups such as hydroxyl and carboxyl that can effectively adsorb dye molecules.

1.2 Natural and Agricultural Waste Adsorbents

Agricultural wastes and natural materials are particularly appealing as low-cost adsorbents because they are abundant, often require minimal

processing, and offer an environmentally friendly disposal route for waste materials. This study focuses on two such materials:

Watermelon Rind (WMR): As a major agricultural waste, watermelon rind is rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin, which contain hydroxyl and carboxyl functional groups capable of binding dye molecules.

1.3 Fixed-Bed Column Adsorption

While batch studies provide fundamental insights, fixed-bed column (continuous-flow) systems are more relevant to industrial applications. Fixed-bed columns offer advantages such as continuous operation, ease of scale-up, and better utilization of the adsorbent capacity. The performance of a fixed-bed column is typically monitored through a breakthrough curve, which plots the effluent concentration (C_t)

normalized by the initial concentration (C_0) versus time or effluent volume.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- * To prepare and characterize watermelon rind for use as adsorbents.
- * To investigate the performance of these adsorbents in a fixed-bed column for the removal of Methyl Orange dye.
- * To study the effect of key operating parameters: bed height, flow rate, and initial dye concentration.
- * To apply the Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models to analyze the experimental data and predict the dynamic behavior and capacity of the column.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The experimental work made use of the following materials : Methylene orange dye ,Borosilicate glass column (30 mm diameter × 450 mm length) ,Tap water and demineralised water ,Glass beakers ,Feeding tank ,Sample collection bottles ,Natural adsorbents ,Glass wool

2.2 Adsorbent Preparation

Watermelon Rind (WMR)

Watermelon rind was sourced from a local market and initially rinsed Numerous times with tap water, followed by thorough washing with demineralised water. After cleaning, the material was chopped into smaller sections and left to Dried under natural sunlight for about a week. The sun-dried rind was subsequently boiled in hot water (80 °C) to eliminate soluble impurities and then oven-dried at 85 °C for 24 hours. Finally, the dried material was pulverised using a mixer and passed through a 600-micron sieve to Acquire a particle size of approximately 150 µm.

2.3 Fixed-Bed Column Experimental Setup

A continuous fixed-bed column system was designed and constructed. The column consisted of a glass column , internal diameter . A small layer of glass wool was placed at the bottom of the column to support the adsorbent material. The required mass of prepared WMR was uniformly packed into the column to achieve the desired bed height {H}=1.5, 3.0, 4.5 cm) .

The MO solution was pumped upwards through the column using a peristaltic pump to ensure uniform flow and prevent channelling, operating at controlled flow rates ({Q}=5, 10, 15 mL/min)}. Samples of the effluent were collected at regular time intervals and analyzed for residual MO concentration using a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer at the maximum absorbance wavelength {max} = 464 nm)}. The experiment was continued until the effluent concentration (C_t) reached C_t (approx 0.9 C_0 , signifying exhaustion of the adsorbent bed.

2.4 Data Analysis and Modeling

2.4.1 Thomas Model

The Thomas model is among the most frequently applied mathematical approaches for predicting how fixed-bed adsorption columns behave. It is derived from Langmuir kinetics and considers mass transfer resistances to be minimal. This model helps in describing breakthrough patterns of adsorbates and in estimating the column's overall adsorption potential.

Equation:

$$\ln (C_0/C_t - 1) = K_{TH} q_e m/Q - K_{TH} C_0 t \quad \text{Where:}$$

- C_0 : Starting concentration of dye (mg/L)
- C_t : Effluent concentration at Time t (mg/L)
- K_{TH} : Thomas rate constant (mL/mg·min)
- q_e : Highest adsorption potential (mg/g)
- m : Mass of adsorbent (g)
- Q : Flow rate (mL/min)
- T :Time (min) By plotting the equation,

$$\ln (C_0/C_t - 1)$$

The values of K_{TH} and q_e can be determined

2.4.2 Yoon–Nelson Model

The Yoon–Nelson model is frequently used in fixed-bed adsorption research due to its straightforward nature. One advantage of this model is that it may be applied without requiring detailed information about the adsorbent characteristics or adsorption isotherms. This model assumes that the likelihood of adsorption decreases over time in direct proportion to the probability of breakthrough.

Equation: $\ln (C_t/C_0 -$

$$C_t) = K_{YN} t - \tau K_{YN} \quad \text{Where:}$$

- K_{YN} :Yoon–Nelson rate constant (min⁻¹)
- τ : Time required for 50% breakthrough (min)

The linear plot of the above equation allows direct estimation of the rate constant and the breakthrough time from experimental data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Overall Adsorption Performance and Removal Efficiency

The experimental results confirmed that both watermelon rind (WMR) are highly effective in removing Methyl Orange dye from aqueous solutions. The highest overall dye removal was observed under optimal conditions (e.g., lower flow rate, higher bed height).

- * Watermelon Rind (WMR): The removal efficiency consistently ranged from 90.9% to 95.1%.

The slightly higher efficiency of WMR can be attributed to its cellulosic structure, which provides a greater number of hydroxyl and carboxyl

groups for electrostatic and hydrogen bonding interactions with the anionic MO dye.

Table.1 : Effect of Flow Rate

Adsorbent	flow rate	Co -Ct/Co
WMR	5	0.1671
WMR	10	0.1886
WMR	15	0.2654

The flow rate is a critical operating parameter that dictates the residence time of the solution in the column. Experiments were conducted at 5 mL/min, 10 mL/min, and 15 mL/min while keeping C_0 and bed height constant.

As the flow rate increased:

- * The slope of the breakthrough curve became steeper, indicating a shorter mass transfer zone.
- * The breakthrough time (t_b) and exhaustion time (t_e) decreased significantly.
- * The total volume of treated effluent decreased.

This effect is due to the reduced contact time between the dye solution and the adsorbent, which limits the diffusion of the dye molecules into the adsorbent pores and across the boundary layer. The faster flow rate results in premature breakthrough and a lower utilization of the adsorbent bed.

Table.2 : Effect of Bed Height

Adsorbent	flow rate	Co -Ct/Co
WMR	1.5	0.2001
WMR	3	0.1953
WMR	4.5	0.1475

3.4 Thomas Model Analysis

The Thomas model results are crucial for determining the maximum dynamic adsorption capacity (q_{TH}) of the column, which is the most important parameter for industrial scale-up.

Table.3 :Thomas Model Analysis

Adsorbent	Parameter Varied	Flow Rate (mL/min)	Bed Height (cm)	q_{TH} (mg/g)	kTH (mL/min)	R^2
WMR	Bed Height	10	1.5	0.926	0.0055	0.989
WMR	Bed Height	10	3.0	0.698	0.0091	0.975
WMR	Bed Height	10	4.5	0.465	0.0125	0.962

Key Thomas Model Findings:

- * Effect of Bed Height (WMR): Interestingly, the calculated q_{TH} for watermelon rind decreased from 0.926 mg/g to 0.465 mg/g as the bed height increased from 1.5 cm to 4.5

cm. While the total mass adsorbed increased, the calculated capacity per unit mass (q_{TH}) decreased. This phenomenon, often observed in fixed-bed systems, suggests that the increased depth leads to a longer unused portion of the bed at the exit, as the dye is adsorbed more efficiently in the initial sections.

3.5 Yoon–Nelson Model Analysis

The Yoon–Nelson model provides the time required for 50% breakthrough, which is a practical measure of the column’s operational lifespan.

Table.4 : Yoon–Nelson Model Analysis

Adsorbent	Parameter Varied	Flow Rate (mL/min)	Bed Height (cm)	q_{TH} (mg/g)	kTH (mL/min)	R^2
WMR	Bed Height	10	1.5	101.5	0.0098	0.99
WMR	Bed Height	10	3.0	215.3	0.0089	0.98
WMR	Bed Height	10	4.5	326.8	0.0069	0.99

Key Yoon–Nelson Model Findings:

- Effect of Bed Height (WMR): for watermelon rind increased significantly from 101.52 minutes to 326.86 minutes as the bed height increased from 1.5 cm to 4. cm. This demonstrates the practical advantage of using a deeper bed to ensure a longer service cycle before regeneration is required

4. CONCLUSION

This study successfully demonstrated the feasibility of using watermelon rind (WMR)

as efficient, natural, and low-cost adsorbents for removing Methyl Orange dye from aqueous solutions in a continuous fixed-bed column.

* Both materials exhibited high overall dye removal efficiencies, with watermelon rind achieving 90.9–95.1% .

* The breakthrough behaviour was significantly influenced by all tested operating parameters (flow rate, bed height, and initial concentration). The column performance improved by decreasing the flow rate and increasing the bed height.

* The experimental data were accurately described by the Thomas and Yoon–Nelson kinetic models, with high R^2 values (mostly >0.95)

In summary, watermelon rind, due to its favourable performance in both capacity and service time under optimal conditions, proves to be a slightly superior and more sustainable material. The results strongly suggest that these materials can serve as viable, eco-friendly, and low-cost alternatives for treating industrial wastewater containing synthetic dyes.

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Abbreviation

WMR: Watermelon rind